

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

N^o 3(12)

27.03.2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
N^o 078777

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

- ✓ ANIQ FANLAR
- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOIIY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
- ✓ PEDAGOGIKA FANLARI

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Muxtarov
t.f.b. PhD

Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
olingan

Murojaat uchun

 [@fer_teach_uz](https://t.me/fer_teach_uz)
 +99893-343-13-14
 <https://fer-teach.uz/rai>

Mas'ul muharrir

S.I.Zokirov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Taxrir hay'ati:

T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston

T.Yu.Bakirov - ped. f.b. PhD, FarDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

B.B.Mallabayev - tarix f.n., dotsent. NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

X.K.Boymirzayev - ped. f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

I.U.Kuzikulov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

G.K.Obidova- p.f.b. PhD, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

B.T.Mirzadjanov - tarix f.b. PhD, , NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

M.A.Maxmudov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

B.Ya.Tursunov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b.PhD, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston

Sh.A.Umarov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

I.A.Rustamov - fal.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Sh.J.Kholmatov - i.i.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Z.N.Khatamova- t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

B.X.Tolipov - f.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.M.Umurzakova - t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

L.P.Mamasaidov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

GROWTH HORMONE – 30 YEARS OF CLINICAL PRACTICE: PAST, PRESENT, FUTURE

Kurbanova Nozima Sabirdjanovna

*Scientific adviser, Assistant of the Department of Endocrinology,
Samarkand State Medical University*

Djurayeva Aziza

Samarkand State Medical University

Nosirova Nafisaxon

Samarkand State Medical University

Urinova Nasiba

Samarkand State Medical University

Asrorova Marhabo

Samarkand State Medical University

Annotation. *The era of recombinant technologies, which began in the second half of the 20th century, made it possible to produce recombinant growth hormone (rGH), necessary for the treatment of short stature of various origins. The time has come for virtually unlimited possibilities for obtaining rGH, which has served as an incentive to study the effectiveness and safety of rGH use, and to search for optimal methods of its use and dosage regimens. Many years of experience in the use of somatropin in clinical practice have made it possible to obtain data on its effectiveness, primarily in somatotropic insufficiency in children, to study its effect on the functional state of various organs and systems, and to expand the indications for the use of rGH.*

Keywords: *a growth hormone; short stature; GH deficiency; Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome; Laron syndrome; idiopathic short stature; intrauterine growth retardation.*

ГОРМОН РОСТА – 30 ЛЕТ КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ ПРАКТИКИ: ПРОШЛОЕ, НАСТОЯЩЕЕ, БУДУЩЕЕ

Курбанова Нозима Сабирджановна

*Научный руководитель, ассистент кафедры эндокринологии,
Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет*

Джусраева Азиза

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Носирова Нафисахон

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Уринова Насиба

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Асророва Мархабо

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Аннотация. Эпоха рекомбинантных технологий, начавшаяся во второй половине XX века, позволила производить рекомбинантный гормон роста (рГР), необходимый для лечения низкорослости различного происхождения. Настало время практически неограниченных возможностей получения рГР, что послужило стимулом к изучению эффективности и безопасности применения рГР, поиску оптимальных методов его применения и режимов дозирования. Многолетний опыт применения соматропина в клинической практике позволил получить данные о его эффективности, прежде всего при соматотропной недостаточности у детей, изучить его влияние на функциональное состояние различных органов и систем, расширить показания к применению. использование рГР.

Ключевые слова: гормон роста; невысокий рост; дефицит гормона роста; синдром Шерешевского-Тернера; синдром Ларона; идиопатическая низкорослость; задержка внутриутробного развития

Introduction. The virtually unlimited possibilities for obtaining rGH have served as an incentive to study the effectiveness and safety of therapy using it, and to search for optimal ways of using it and dosage regimens. Recombinant human growth hormone (rGH) was first synthesized in 1981 by the biotechnological corporation Genentech (San Francisco, California) [1]. Previously, growth hormone extracted from the cadaveric pituitary glands of humans was used to treat pituitary dwarfism [2]. In 1975 N.A. Zarubina published the first domestic monograph on the topic “Pituitary dwarfism (clinic, diagnosis, differential diagnosis, treatment),” which summarized the experience of treating pituitary dwarfs. However, the use of human growth hormone obtained from cadaveric pituitary glands was accompanied by a number of limitations and risks, and the development of Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease in patients prompted the search for alternative ways to obtain GH. Therefore, GH received widespread use in clinical practice only in the late 80s - early

90s last century, after recombinant technologies made it possible to produce it in unlimited quantities. Growth hormone became the second recombinant drug to be introduced into clinical practice, following insulin. As restrictions in the production of growth hormone have disappeared, a phase of active clinical research has begun to optimize treatment in terms of dosage, timing of administration and duration of use of the drug. In subsequent years, rGH was approved for the treatment of various forms of short stature and has been shown to improve both final height and influence many metabolic processes in the body including improving psychological and social parameters.

Epidemiology. According to foreign sources, the prevalence of somatotropic deficiency is 1–4 cases per 10,000 children [4]. In Uzbekistan, growth hormone deficiency is 1–2 cases per 10,000 children. The prevalence of somatotropic deficiency in Uzbekistan over a 9-year period (2014–2022) is 17.5 per 100,000 children and is not the same in different federal districts of the country (Fig. 1). The maximum prevalence of the disease was detected in the North-West region - 20.4 per 100,000 children, the lowest in the Kashkadara region (9.8 per 100,000 children) and the Southern Federal District (11.8 per 100,000 children). GH deficiency in children Treatment of GH deficiency in children is the first and main indication for growth hormone replacement therapy [5, 6]. Long-term observations confirm that with a timely diagnosis, children can achieve growth

targets. Many years of experience in treating children with somatotrophic insufficiency at the Institute of Pediatric Endocrinology has proven the effectiveness and safety of long-term therapy with rGH in a large cohort of Russian patients. A detailed analysis of long-term growth hormone therapy in 422 patients (202 girls and 220 boys) showed that the total increase in height was 58.4 cm in males and 52.8 cm in females. As a result, the final height in adolescents was treated for an average of 7 years (from 6.0 to 10.5 boys and from 5.0 to 10.0 years girls), was 174.7 cm (173.0–179.5 cm) in boys and 162.3 cm (158.8–164.4 cm) for girls. At the same time, the difference between the predicted final height and the achieved height was only 1.3 cm for boys and 0.8 cm for girls. And for some adolescents, the SDS of final height even exceeded the SDS of genetically predicted height. The metabolic effect of somatropin led to an increase in the overall tone of the body, an increase in muscle strength, normalization of lipid and carbohydrate metabolism, an increase in cardiac output and improved bone mineralization. Over the past 30 years, the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan has been conducting systematic work to study the functional system that regulates the synthesis and secretion of GH, including regulatory proteins of the hypothalamus, pituitary hormones, growth and transcription factors, as well as a wide range of metabolic and systemic effects of GH in different age periods. Early 1990s marked the beginning of active study of the causes of pituitary dwarfism.

HGH deficiency in adults. Growth hormone is synthesized throughout life and has not only a growth-stimulating effect. It determines the size and strength of muscle mass, bone mass and mineral density [35], regulates fat and carbohydrate metabolism, the volume of extracellular fluid [36], affects various functions of the central nervous system, and has an effect on immunity. As an anabolic hormone, it is necessary throughout the life of an adult. The life expectancy of patients with pituitary dwarfism without treatment is 20–30 years shorter than the general population. The first placebo-controlled long-term studies on the treatment of GH deficiency in adult patients date back to 1989 [37, 38]. In the Russian Federation, studying the effect of GH deficiency in adult patients with somatotrophic insufficiency began in the late 90s. XX century. Research by E.V. Nagaeva included the study of body composition, selection of the optimal dose of rGH in adult patients, and features of the course of hypopituitarism [39, 40]. By

2005, the results were summed up and the effectiveness and safety of the use of rGH in people over 18 years of age was proven (O.B.

Providing patients with growth hormone in the RF. Over the past 15 years in the Russian Federation, all children with proven somatotrophic insufficiency (pituitary dwarfism) have been provided with somatotropin free of charge, which is included in the list of drugs centrally purchased from the federal budget (the current document is Order of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 2738 -r dated December 10, 2018). State support for patients with growth hormone deficiency began on a large scale at the end of 2008, when the “High-Cost Nosologies” (HCN) program was created; initially it included 7 nosologies, including “pituitary dwarfism.” After some time - in 2019 - the program already included 12 high-cost nosologies, and in 2020 - 14 nosologies. At the same time, pituitary dwarfism has always been and remains an integral part of the program, which allows us to fully provide all children with somatotrophic deficiency with the necessary treatment and analyze the effectiveness of rGH therapy. Employees of the Russian Ministry of Health, together with experts - pediatric endocrinologists from the Institute of Pediatric Endocrinology - for the purpose of public procurement, conduct an annual examination of all cases of somatotrophic insufficiency in children in Russia, followed by providing them with growth hormone. Since 2023, financing of these purchases began to be carried out with the participation of the “Circle of Good” fund for supporting children with severe life-threatening and chronic diseases, including rare (orphan) diseases. Starting from 2022, adults with newly diagnosed GH deficiency, as well as young people over 18 years of age with somatotrophic insufficiency, after retesting and confirmation of somatotrophic insufficiency, have the opportunity to provide rGH within the framework of the “14 high-cost nosologies” program. Adolescents with a confirmed molecular genetic cause of the disease and a number of other conditions specified in the Consensus on the diagnosis of somatotrophic deficiency are not subject to retesting [32]. The registry of patients with somatotrophic deficiency at the end of 2023 included 4639 patients (4520 children and 119 adults).

Growth hormone in diseases not related to somatotrophic insufficiency.

New advances have led to increased clinical use of growth hormone, opening up new possibilities for treating other forms of short stature. This is important

progress that cannot be ignored. Back in 1983, at the International Conference on the Use of Growth Hormone, the question arose about the need for its use in short children who do not have GH deficiency. The availability of rGH has allowed research into its effectiveness for various non-pituitary causes of short stature. The goal of therapy for short children without somatotropic insufficiency is to increase the growth rate and normalize linear growth without affecting the underlying causes of their disease. Recombinant GH is used in a variety of conditions, such as syndromic short stature (eg, Shereshevsky-Turner, Silver-Russell, Prader-Willi, De Gruchy syndromes), chronic renal failure, history of long-term glucocorticoid therapy, intrauterine growth restriction, idiopathic short stature, juvenile idiopathic arthritis, diseases of the hematopoietic system, neurofibromatosis, cystic fibrosis, etc. In all these diseases, short stature is not caused by somatotropic deficiency; such patients are characterized by a dose-dependent nature of the effectiveness of GH and very careful monitoring is carried out.

INTRAuterine growth retardation (IUGR). Short stature caused by intrauterine growth retardation is identified as a separate nosology. The first large randomized trial of long-term use of rGH in this cohort of children dates back to 1990. A history of IUGR is associated with an increased risk of developing short stature, early onset with rapid progression of puberty, neurocognitive dysfunction, metabolic changes (reduced bone density, carbohydrate metabolism disorders, dyslipidemia), increased risk of cardiovascular disease in later life. The vast majority of children with IUGR experience spontaneous catch-up development in the first years of life. At the Samarkand State Medical University "SFRSNPTSE" of the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan, over the past 20 years, observation and, if necessary, treatment of short children with IUGR have been carried out. E.V. Nagaeva studied a wide range of clinical, hormonal, and metabolic features in patients with IUGR [49]. Many years of experience in the use of rGH in children with IUGR have proven that predictors of the effectiveness of therapy are the dose of the drug and the timing of initiation of therapy (as with GH deficiency, early initiation of therapy is preferable) [50].

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондииков Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исматова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.
11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *MiastoPrzyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A Clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.

14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149). 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferentsionaldiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.1. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdulkakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
21. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
22. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.
23. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
24. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
25. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovna XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):341-345.
26. Sobirjonovna KN. FACTORS Determining the clinical significance of deipeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
27. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).

28. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
29. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. Asia Journal of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR). 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
30. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. JournalNX. Published online 2020:460-461.
31. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. Educational Research in Universal Sciences. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):259-264.
32. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149). 2023;1(9):121-123.
33. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfiyeva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. Science and Education. 2023;4(12):107-117.
34. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
35. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. Pedagog. 2022;5(5):346-348.
36. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. Texa Jour of Mutl Stud. 2023;25:39-43.
37. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. Science and Education. 2023;4(3).
38. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. 1. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
39. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149). 2023;1(8):148-153.
40. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o'zgarishlar. so'ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi. 2023;6(12):417-422.
41. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziyabilan birgalikdakechish xususiyatlarivaularnidavolashusullari. Science and Education. 2023;4(2):516-519.
42. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda covid-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. Gospodarka i Innowacje. 2023;34:78-81.

43. G.Sh N, D.e S, Alisherovich BA, Erkin R is the son of S, Bektash U is the son of S. Relationship between diabetic nephropathy and cardiac disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Pedagog.* 2022;5(5):337-340.
44. Daminov AT, Sa'dullayeva SM qizi, Ismoilova SI qizi. Samarqand viloyatida qandli diabet asoratlari uchrash chastotasi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):139-142.
45. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, O'g'li IBI, Qizi ADD. The role of gastrointestinal hormones in the pathology of the digestive system. *Pedagog.* 2022;5(6):408-412.
46. Ulugbekovna NP, Bakhtiyorovna RI, Almosovich RA, Takhirovich DA. Thyroid Diseases during Pregnancy and their Impact on Maternal and Fetal Outcomes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149). 2023;1(8):188-190.
47. Nilufar R, Adkhamjon K. TO The development of cardiovascular diseases effects of environmental factors. *Fan, ta'lim, madaniyat va innovatsiya jurnali | journal of science, education, culture and innovation.* 2022;1(4):100-101.
48. Xoldorov X, Omonov F, Jumayev I, Daminov AT. Type 1 diabetes as a risk factor for bone health in childhood. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal.* 2023;2(8):131-135.
49. Daminov AT, Xurramova S, Islomov A, Ulashev M, Ikramov R, Mirzakhakimov P. Type 2 diabetes and bone mineral density in postmenopausal women. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(11).
50. Berkinov A, Safarov F, Tursunova S, Daminov AT. Vitamin d status in senior residents of samarkand region. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal.* 2023;2(8):136-140.
51. Taxirovich DA, N SY, I IM, Z SM. Vitamin-D yetishmovchiligining qandli diabet 1-tip rivojlanishiga ta'siri. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.* 2023;34:74-77.

Tadqiq va tatbiq
ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tom 02. | Son. 03. | 2024

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

Vol. 02. | Iss. 03. | 2024

Исследования и внедрение
научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 03. | 2024

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tahririyat manzili:

150100, Farg‘ona vil., Farg‘ona sh., Solim ko‘chasi, 23/4-uy, 26-xonadon

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Bizning web-sahifa:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali "Fer-Teach" MChJ muassisligida tashkil etilgan bo‘lib, ilmiy va uslubiy jihatdan Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Farg‘ona filiali tomonidan qo‘llab-quvvatlanadi. Mazkur jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023-yil 3-mayda ommaviy axborot vositasi sifatida davlat ro‘yxatidan (№ 078777) o‘tkazilgan.

ISSN 3030-3362.

Jurnal aniq va tabiiy fanlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy fanlar, texnika fanlari, tibbiyot fanlari, pedagogika fanlari sohalarini qamrab oladi. Tahrir hay‘ati a‘zolidan respublikaning turli OTMlarida faoliyat olib boruvchi fan nomzodlari va doktorlari o‘rin olishgan..

Nashr tillari: O‘zbek, Rus, Ingliz va Qoraqalpoq tillari

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 03. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 03. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 03. 2024

Научно-методический журнал “ Исследования и внедрение ”

Адрес редакции:

150100, Ферганская область, г. Фергана, улица Солим, дом 23/4, кв. 26

Е-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Наш сайт:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

Учредителем научно-технического журнала

«Исследования и внедрение» является ООО “Fer-Teach”.

Журнал издается с 2023 года, зарегистрирован 3 мая 2023 года Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан (Сертификат № 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области техники и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физике, математике, информационных технологиях. В журнале также публикуются научные статьи по лингвистике, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

Языки издания: Узбекский, русский, английский и каракалпакский

Tadqiq va tatbiq
ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tom 02. | Son. 03. | 2024

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

Vol. 02. | Iss. 03. | 2024

Исследования и внедрение
научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 03. | 2024

Scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation”

Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, building 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Our website:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

The scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation” was founded by Fer-Teach LLC and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник. Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyliги uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.